

PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PROFILING METHODS IN PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHODIAGNOSTICS

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Abstract. *The profiling method is one of the newly developing interesting and practical branches of the field of psychology. It is studied not only in the science of social psychology, but also in the system of philosophy, pedagogy, logic, criminalistics. In this article, according to the opinion of the author, one of the methods that modern pedagogues need to learn is information about the practical importance of profiling methods in pedagogical activity.*

Keywords: *Profiling, profiler, verbal, nonverbal, psych diagnostics, introvert, extrovert, method.*

ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МЕТОДОВ ПРОФИЛИРОВАНИЯ В ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПСИХОДИАГНОСТИКЕ

Аннотация. *Метод профилирования является одной из новых развивающихся интересных и практических областей области психологии. Она изучается не только в науке социальной психологии, но и в системе философии, педагогики, логики, криминалистики. В данной статье, по мнению автора, одним из методов, который необходимо усвоить современным педагогам, является информация о практическом значении методов профилирования в педагогической деятельности.*

Ключевые слова: *Профилирование, профайлер, вербальный, невербальный, психодиагностика, интроверт, экстраверт, метод.*

INTRODUCTION.

Faces are as legible as books, only with these circumstances to recommend them to our perusal, that they are read in much less time, and are much less likely to deceive us. (Kaspar Lavater)

Profiling (English "profile") or profile method - is a method of creating a profile of a person that allows one to make predictions in advance using several psychological methods, such as psychological assessment of individuals, observation, analysis of changes in their behavior based on their appearance and behavior.

The profiling method consists of two complementary methods, namely, psychological observation and survey (interview) method.

Profiling includes rapid psych diagnostics, emotion analysis, manipulative techniques, nanotechnology, eloquence, graphology, facial expression analysis, muscle analysis, and social psychology. The method of profiling occupies an important place in the activity of every pedagogue. That is why the psychological laws and mechanisms of this method are involved in the process of the activity. With the help of this method, the pedagogue enters into interpersonal relations based on the laws of psychology. In the process of profiling, all cognitive qualities of the pedagogue (memory, attention, perception, intuition, thinking, imagination) are involved. These processes help the employee to think logically, to connect the situation with the past situation, and to perfectly perceive the qualification, object, and conditions of mutual

comparison. Profiling or the profile method is a psychological assessment of students, observation, and analysis of changes in their behavior based on external expressions and behavior, and allows to predict and visually determine the "psychological portrait" of students.

The practical advantage of this method is that, first of all, pedagogues must know the non-verbal means of human communication at the stage of psychological preparation. Any communication always includes the process of mutual adaptation of the object and the subject. It is not necessary to have special abilities or to read a lot of books to predict the behavior of a person and his actions in advance. The main goal of studying the use of the profiling method in the activities of pedagogues is to determine their unique characteristics using verbal and non-verbal means of communication and to develop a mechanism of psychological influence depending on it. [2]

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURES. Currently, in our country, since a reliable guide on the application of profiling methods in the field of education, especially in pedagogical psych diagnostics processes, and the literature is insufficient for conducting research and obtaining general information, we present the following literature to the interested.

1. *Joe Navarro: "I See What You're Thinking"*

The book is written simply and clearly. Stories from Navarro's past share theories about hand gestures, foot gestures, acting on certain emotions, and much other non-verbal communication. Reading the book will give clear results and help you make visual diagnoses, if not make you a pro profiler.

2. *Paul Ekman: "The Psychology of Emotions." "I Know How You Feel"*

The title of the book fully expresses the content of the work and the purpose of the author. Renowned profiler Paul Ekman teaches us how to identify people's emotions, even when they try to hide them from us.

The Psychology of Emotions book is also one of the basics of profiling, and I recommend reading it to anyone interested in the subject. In Ekman's book, you'll learn about micro expressions, recognition of emotion, and more.

The book is illustrated with examples: you will not only read some manifestations of emotions but also see them. Of course, it helps to acquire the skill of recognizing emotions faster.

3. *Desmond Morris: "Body Language"*

The most important work is on non-verbal signals. The author examines the variety of body movements and explains what meanings they can have.

For example, Body language refers to an expressive, imitative, symbolic, hybrid, compound, conductor, greeting, and many other non-verbal signs. In this book, all the actions of students, from movement to eating, are described and explained by humans. If you want to become a non-verbal expert, then this basic study will give you much of the knowledge you need.

4. *Alan and Barbara Pease: "Body Language"*

The title is the same as Morris's book. The content is also similar, but there are some differences. This book has a different structure: Morris has organized the actions by their meaning, while Alan and Barbara have organized them by their place. Both this and the previous book come with illustrations.

By studying these books, you can gain fundamental knowledge on how to "read" people and understand their true emotional state. It also shows how to analyze our behavior: sometimes we do not understand what we feel (or we are afraid to admit it to ourselves). Thus, "Body language" will tell you a lot of new and interesting things about yourself and people.

We can observe that during the analysis of this literature. Most of the research and experiments were conducted in other fields rather than in the field of pedagogy. So!

What is the need for pedagogues to study the above-mentioned literatures? First of all, for the lesson to be effective, it is necessary to establish positive communication between the teacher and students. We know that there are verbal and non-verbal forms of communication. A pedagogue who can control his actions in non-verbal communication can control the lesson. This, in turn, requires the pedagogue to learn profiling methods. It is observed that students' individual-psychological qualities are manifested in the communication during the lesson. During communication, students are perceived differently: some are "open" to communication, i.e. **extroverts**, it is easy to form a first impression about them; others seem to be "closed" to communication, that is, **introverts**, it is difficult to give any specific opinion about them.

According to Albert Mehrabian, in the process of conveying information, verbal means (only words) are 7%, vocal means (the soul of the voice, including intonation) are 38%, and non-verbal means are 55%. Professor Berdwissl conducted analogical research on the relative share of non-verbal means in human communication. He notes that an average person speaks only 10-11 minutes a day using words, and each sentence sounds on average 2.5 seconds. Like Mehrabian, he found that less than 35% of the conversation is verbal communication, and more than 65% of information is conveyed through nonverbal communication.[1]

"A gesture is not a movement of the body, but of the soul." It indicates a person's desire and what he feels at the moment, and a gesture that is typical for someone indicates a characteristic aspect of his character.

ANALYSIS OF OBSERVATION RESULTS: In observation studies of the lesson process, in two age groups (12 and 18 years old; in total, 4 subgroups, each with 20 students) the teacher's emotional state affects the quality of the lesson and interaction with students To study the effect on communicative communication, empirical studies were conducted. At the beginning of the study, a subject was selected that was interesting for all students and had an average rating of 75%, was involved in the process. The results showed that the impact of the teacher's emotional state on students of different ages was determined to be of different importance. During the research, empirical data that were not foreseen at the beginning of the experimental test were obtained, and their description was not included in the scope of this work. Below you will see only the emotional state of the teacher, and how practical it is in the learning process of students:

In the first group of 12-year-olds, the rate of mastering the lesson before the experiment was 78%, and after the experiment, it decreased to 13%.

In the second group of 12-year-olds, the rate of mastering the lesson before the experimental test was 73%, and after the experiment, this rate decreased by 15%.

In the first group of 18-year-olds, the rate of mastery before the experiment was 78%, but after the experiment, it decreased to 24%.

In the second group of 18-year-olds, the rate of mastering the lesson before the experimental test was 76%, and after the experiment, this rate decreased to 30%.

CONCLUSION:

From the results of the above-mentioned observations, we can come to the following conclusion. It is important to use profiling in teacher-student relationship situations. Such methods make it possible to reveal hidden motives, detect lies, and correctly assess a person without the use of psychological tests. We conclude that training in profiling methods should be mandatory for pedagogues of special services who need to quickly assess a person, his characteristics, strengths, and weaknesses, as well as understand what to expect from him in an extreme or stressful situation. These ideas have been proven in the above experiments. Therefore, it is important for a pedagogue not only to learn to analyze the behavior and gestures of students but also to be able to control their behavior. In the empirical research conducted above, we observed that the pedagogue's lack of control over his gestures harmed the motivation of students in their learning activities. We have concluded that for a modern pedagogue who can fully meet the demands of the present time, it is not only the perfect mastery of specialist knowledge but also the study of profiling methods that is of great practical importance.

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